

STUDY OF THE ENERGY ABSORPTION CAPABILITY OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH FOAM CORE AND CFRP FACE SHEETS

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Introduction and methodology

To improve the efficiency of vehicles, the development of lightweight structures is desired. In order to achieve that goal without compromising the protection of occupants during impacts, advanced materials need to be used (e.g. carbon fibre, polymeric crushable foams). Hence, material exploration, experimental tests and numerical modelling techniques need to be optimised to design new low-weight structures capable of absorbing high amounts of energy during crash events.

A sandwich structure is desired for absorbing energy during the side pole impact test. Experiments and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) are used to design a structure consisting of a core made of polymeric foam and CFRP skins

Fig. 1 Schematic of the reduced-scale quasi-static test

Experimental results

Two configurations were considered:

- Structure loaded on top of a CFRP rib
- Structure loaded between two CFRP ribs

Fig. 2 Response of the crash structures at an indenter displacement of: (a) 8 mm; (b) 20 mm

Two regions with interfacial failure within the composite skins were identified on each side of the panel:

Fig. 3 Post-test specimen

Fig. 4 Load-displacement response

Correlation between FEA and experimental tests

A numerical model was created using Abaqus/Explicit. The core was modelled with solid elements and the "Crushable Foam" material model, whereas the composite skins were modelled with conventional shell elements and "ABQ_PLY_FABRIC". Cohesive elements were also included in the FE model to simulate both delamination within the skin and debonding between the foam and the composite parts

Fig. 5 Comparison of the deformed shape at an indenter displacement of: (a) 1 mm; (b) 20 mm

Fig. 6 Load-displacement correlation for specimen: (a) loaded on one rib; (b) loaded between two ribs

Key findings

- From the experimental tests, it was found that both configurations followed the same features: delamination of the top and bottom plies of the composite skin, followed by further delamination along a second weak interface and fibre breakage under the indenter
- Numerical results correlated well with the experimental ones with regards to failure mechanisms, load-displacement curves and energy absorption
- FEA was employed to assess the extent of the separation between the core and the composite skins: the extent of the debonded area was 12 mm larger for the panel with two ribs
- Numerical models were used to study the individual contribution of the three elements of the sandwich panel to the overall energy absorbed by the structure, with carbon fibre absorbing most of the energy
- These experimental studies and correlations with FEA provided important information about the response of these complex structures, validating the methodology to create accurate numerical models
- The outcomes will be used to design an impact test based on similar mixed-mode loading conditions

Structure	Energy absorption from tests (J)	Energy absorption from FE (J)	Difference (%)
One rib	1,679 ± 47	1,729	3
Two ribs	1,627 ± 21	1,569	4

Table 1 Comparison of the energy absorbed by the structure between tests and FEA

Structure	Energy absorbed by foam (J)	Energy absorbed by CFRP (J)	Energy absorbed by cohesive (J)
One rib	91	1,620	18
Two ribs	105	1,445	18

Table 2 Energy absorbed by the different materials, extracted from FE models